

Research Article

"The Lip Balm Highlighter"- Merging Cosmetics and Functionality

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Abstract: *The Lip Balm Highlighter is a dual-purpose product with two sides: one dedicated to lip care and the other to highlighting. Primarily targeting students, this product offers a convenient and cost-effective solution by reducing the need to carry multiple items. In today's fast-paced world, students often face the challenge of carrying numerous personal care and stationery items, which can be both cumbersome and costly. This product addresses the growing demand for multitasking products in the cosmetic and stationery industries, aligning with the trend towards simplicity and functionality. Moreover, the need for eco-friendly and sustainable products is more urgent than ever as the world seeks ways to reduce waste. The Lip Balm Highlighter's potential for commercialization lies in its alignment with this global movement, offering both convenience and an environmentally conscious choice. By reducing the number of single-use products and packaging, the Lip Balm Highlighter can significantly contribute to waste reduction. The target market includes students, eco-conscious consumers, and professionals seeking to streamline their daily essentials while supporting sustainability. The time to produce and market this product is now, as it taps into both a functional and environmental need.*

Keywords: Dual-purpose, Sustainability, Convenience

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Lip Balm Highlighter is a novel cosmetic product that combines two functionalities—lip balm for moisturizing lips and a highlighter for educational or office use. This dual-purpose product reflects the growing trend of multifunctional items in the cosmetic industry, where consumers seek convenience and practicality in their everyday products.

Innovations in lip cosmetics have primarily focused on creating multitasking products that address both aesthetic and functional needs. For example, tinted lip balms provide hydration and subtle colour to the lips, showcasing the industry's focus on convenience. The Lip Balm Highlighter follows this trend by incorporating a cosmetic feature (lip balm) with a utility function (highlighter), making it a standout in both the cosmetic and stationery markets.

Recent trends in the cosmetic industry highlight a growing interest in eco-friendly and sustainable products. Many companies are turning to natural ingredients such as plant-based oils and sustainable packaging to meet consumer demand for environmentally responsible products (Sasounian R. et al.,2024). The Lip Balm Highlighter could align with this trend by utilizing sustainable materials for both the balm and the highlighter components, further enhancing its market appeal.

Lip balm formulation has a long history, with continuous innovations in the use of natural and effective moisturizing agents like beeswax, shea butter, and various plant oils (Mawazi et.al, 2024). These ingredients could be key to the success of the Lip Balm Highlighter, ensuring that the lip care aspect remains effective and appealing to health-conscious consumers. The rise of multifunctional cosmetics products responds to consumer demands for products that save time and space. For instance, the market has widely accepted lip balms with additional benefits, such as added sun protection or tinted colouring. The Lip Balm Highlighter fits into this category by merging personal care with a practical, everyday tool.

In summary, the Lip Balm Highlighter reflects current trends in the cosmetic industry toward multifunctionality, sustainability, and convenience. By merging the practical use of a highlighter with the essential benefits of a lip balm, this product has the potential to disrupt both the cosmetic and stationery markets.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 *The value proposition of the product*

The Lip Balm Highlighter lies in its unique combination of two unrelated yet essential functions—lip care and highlighting. Exposure to the elements can lead to dry, chapped lips for students who often walk between classes. Simultaneously, they need a reliable highlighter to mark important points in their study materials. By merging these two needs into a single product, the Lip Balm Highlighter provides a convenient, affordable, and efficient solution.

A strong value proposition captures the target market's attention by clearly articulating how a product solves a problem or improves a user's situation. In this case, the Lip Balm Highlighter solves the issue of carrying multiple items for two purposes, simplifying what students must carry in their backpacks. This approach appeals to the target demographic, offering a consolidated solution that saves space, reduces cost, and increases convenience

Additionally, the value proposition highlights the product's affordability. Students are typically on a limited budget, and buying separate lip care and highlighting products can be costly. The Lip Balm Highlighter serves two purposes and costs less than purchasing the two products individually, making it a budget-friendly option for students. This dual benefit—functionality and affordability—makes the Lip Balm Highlighter stand out in a crowded market.

2.2 *Features, Advantages, and Benefits of the Product*

The key features of the Lip Balm Highlighter are its dual functionality, compact design, and ease of use. The product is split into two sections: one side contains a moisturizing lip balm, while the other includes a highlighter with bright, smudge-resistant ink. Both sides have separate lids to ensure hygiene and prevent mixing the two substances.

Features:

1. **Dual-functionality:** Serves as both a lip balm and a highlighter, making it a versatile tool.

2. **Compact design:** The product is small enough to fit in a pocket or a small compartment in a backpack.
3. **Separate lids:** Maintains hygiene by securely capping the lip balm and highlighter when not in use.
4. **Available in various colours and flavours:** Offers a range of highlighter ink colours and lip balm flavours, allowing for personalization

Advantages:

1. **Portability:** Students no longer need to carry two separate items for lip care and highlighting, reducing the clutter in their bags.
2. **Cost-effectiveness:** By merging two products into one, the Lip Balm Highlighter is more affordable than buying a separate lip balm and highlighter.
3. **Time-saving:** Eliminates the need to search for two different items, saving students time during their busy day.
4. **Convenience:** The combination of two frequently used items in one product offers great convenience for students who are always on the go.

Benefits:

1. **Health and wellness:** The lip balm aspect helps prevent and treat dry, chapped lips, a common issue for students walking to and from classes, especially in extreme weather.
2. **Study efficiency:** A reliable highlighter is crucial for studying, helping students mark important information in their notes or textbooks.
3. **Environmental impact:** Combining two products into one reduces the amount of packaging required, which may appeal to environmentally conscious consumers.
4. **Aesthetic appeal:** Students can express their individuality with customizable colours and flavours, making the product functional and fun to use.

3. FINDINGS

Initial feedback from the target market indicated that combining both utilities into a single product resonates well with students. Therefore, the Lip Balm Highlighter has strong potential for commercialization due to its innovative nature, practicality, and mass-market appeal. The product taps into two established markets: cosmetic products and stationery. Combining elements from both creates a new niche that can attract consumers from both sides. Moreover, the student demographic is vast and continually replenishing, making it a sustainable target market.

Commercializing this product could begin with a pilot launch at universities and high schools, where the primary consumer base is concentrated. From there, it could expand to broader retail markets such as stationery stores, pharmacies, and online platforms like Amazon. Marketing strategies should focus on demonstrating the product's dual functionality and affordability, which are key selling points that are likely to resonate with students and their parents.

One key advantage of this product is its simplicity, which lowers manufacturing costs and makes it easier to scale production. The design does not require expensive materials or complex manufacturing processes, making maintaining a competitive price point easier while ensuring

profitability. The potential for customization, such as offering different highlighter colours and lip balm flavours, also opens the door for limited-edition runs and collaborations, adding an element of exclusivity that could boost demand

4. DISCUSSION

The Lip Balm Highlighter solves a common problem for students: the inconvenience of carrying multiple items in an already cluttered backpack. Students often find themselves needing both lip balm and a highlighter during their day, and this product conveniently combines the two. By addressing this issue, the Lip Balm Highlighter fills a gap in the market that traditional products have not adequately covered.

From a marketing perspective, this product can be positioned as a must-have item for students, particularly those who are constantly on the go. A successful marketing campaign would highlight its practicality, affordability, and unique combination of two essential items. Social media platforms like Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube, which are popular among students, would be ideal channels for promoting the product. Influencers in the beauty and stationery communities could be enlisted to showcase the product's features and benefits, generating buzz and driving sales. The marketability of the Lip Balm Highlighter is further enhanced by its broad appeal. While it is primarily targeted at students, its usefulness extends to anyone who needs both a lip balm and a highlighter, including professionals, teachers, and office workers. This broader market potential increases the product's viability and scalability.

The primary target market for the Lip Balm Highlighter is students, particularly those in high school and college. This demographic is ideal because students frequently need both lip balm and highlighters in their daily routines. They also appreciate convenient, affordable, and customizable products, all of which are key features of the Lip Balm Highlighter.

In addition to students, the secondary market includes young professionals and office workers who also require highlighters for their work while appreciating the convenience of a built-in lip balm. These consumers value products that save time and space, making the Lip Balm Highlighter a suitable option for them as well.

Given the increasing focus on sustainability and convenience among younger consumers, the product's environmental benefits—such as reduced packaging—could also be a significant selling point. This would attract environmentally conscious buyers who are looking for products that align with their values.

5. CONCLUSION

The Lip Balm Highlighter is a well-thought-out innovation that combines the practicality of a highlighter with the essential self-care of a lip balm. Its unique value proposition, affordability, and convenience make it highly marketable to students and young professionals alike. With strong potential for commercialization and scalability, this product can tap into multiple markets, solving common problems with a creative, dual-purpose design. Through targeted marketing and strategic commercialization, the Lip Balm Highlighter has the potential to become a popular and widely used product in both the cosmetic and stationery markets

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